

THE WORLD BANK

CDA NEWSLETTER

A PUBLICATION OF THE CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE, BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO, NIGERIA

Volume 8 No.2

APRIL - JUNE 2020

ISSN: 2350-210X

CDA Signs MoU with Dantata Foods on Dryland Farming

ALSO INSIDE

- 22 COMMUNITIES BENEFIT FROM CDA'S SEEDS PALLIATIVES
- BUK MANAGEMENT EXTENDS TENURE OF PROF. JIBRIN AS DIRECTOR CDA
- MEMBERS OF BUK COMMUNITY HAIL CDA OVER SUPPLY OF FRESH FARM PRODUCE DURING LOCKDOWN

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

EDITORIAL TEAM

Editor in Chief

Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin

Deputy Editor in Chief

Professor Amina Mustapha

Sub- Editor

Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed

Editor: Nura Garba

Proofreader

Professor Aliyu Kamal

Contributing Editors

Dr. Kabir Mustapha

Dr. Aminu Fagge

Dr. Yusuf Garba

Dr. Murtala Badamasi

Dr. Amina L. Mustapha

CDA Signs MoU with Dantata Foods on Dryland Farming

Bayero University's Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and the Dantata Foods and Allied Products on Friday, 26th June, 2020 signed a Memorandum of Understanding on dryland farming that would boost the activities of the small-holder farmers.

Dantata Foods & Allied Products Limited is a privately owned Agricultural and Food Products Company based in Nigeria having one of the largest Oil Mills in West Africa. It is devoted to producing, processing and marketing of Agro Allied Products with its major operation streams being Import, Export and Packaging of high Quality Food Produce.

The Vice Chancellor of Bayero University, Kano, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, who signed on behalf of CDA, said it was in line with the current global trend of triple helix model in which the government, academia and industries partner for advancement of research activities.

According to him, the National Universities Commission (NUC), Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TetFund) and the Nigeria Economic Group are working together on the triple helix model in order to boost socio-economic development in the country.

The Vice Chancellor noted the University had been enjoying a long standing relationship with the Dantata Group having emerged as the first non-governmental body to invest in the University by building the Departments of Accounting and Business Administration more than 10 years ago.

Professor Bello further said that the CDA has state of the art facilities for various analyses including nutritional analysis of food items for exports.

The Chief Executive Officer of the Dantata Foods and Allied Products, Alhaji Tajuddeen Dantata said the agreement signed would encourage production of drought resistant seeds for farmers experiencing climatic challenges and harsh weather conditions.

He said: "With the collaboration, we will be able to conduct research on crops and pass the information to farmers, thus promoting scientific applications in farming.

"The growing population coupled with increasing need for shelter, exposed farmers to difficulties in accessing arable lands.

"Through the partnership, we will ensure quality assurance in production using inputs and other products in accordance with international best standard," he explained.

Alhaji Dantata also said through the collaboration, his company would look into the possibility of

awarding scholarship to the best students of Bayero University, Kano.

Earlier in his remarks, the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, said the centre's emphasis was to refocus its activity to ensure that industries and practitioners are brought to the fore in order to take up research results to the field. He advised industries to define the type of research they want for them to have real impact.

The Director stated that he was happy that Dantata Group expressed interest to collaborate with the CDA, noting that the centre would provide laboratory services to support the group for its export activities.

22 Communities Benefit from CDA's Seeds Palliatives

It was part of CDA outreach activities to bring farmers closer and help them with new farming techniques and seeds for better output

Twenty two communities have benefitted from the seeds palliatives distributed by the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano to farmers to serve as subsidy as well as ensure that seeds become available to the farmers who no longer have money to purchase seeds for the planting season, having exhausted their savings on food during the recent lockdown due to the spread of covid 19 pandemic.

The communities include: Langel, Yarimawa, Janguza, Danguguwa, Doka, Kunyi and Gabari among others.

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, who led the distribution of the seeds urged the farmers to make judicious use of it as it would increase their revenue generation, saying that the CDA was in the forefront in helping farmers with the new techniques and methods for improved farming activities.

The Director Centre for Dryland Agriculture, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin said it was part of the Centre's outreach activities to bring farmers closer and help them with new farming techniques and seeds for better output.

He said the seeds would help the farmers to upscale their production especially at the 2020 rainy season, which coincided with the difficult times as a result of the coronavirus. The seeds distributed include soybeans, groundnut, millet and sorghum.

The Director said the CDA would continue to strengthen its relationship with the neighbouring communities especially the small-holder farmers for improved farming that would boost food production in the country.

The Deputy Director, Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha said the Centre's outreach activities would continue to impact the lives of small-holder farmers.

Seeds Intervention by CDA Timely – Farmers

Farmers who benefitted from the CDA seed palliatives said the intervention was timely and apt due to the daunting economic challenges posed by the Covid-19 pandemic, commending the centre for giving them improved seeds that would boost their farm production.

According to the beneficiaries, the CDA's intervention has impacted positively on the lives of many people in the communities. They commended the CDA and by extension the University for coming to their aid.

Abubakar Mohammed from Lengel said the Centre has for long time been assisting their communities with improved seeds that helped them greatly in their farming activities.

Amina Doka, on her part, said the last time CDA went and distributed improved seeds, she and many others got three times revenue when they sold their crops.

Malam Ibrahim Yarimawa, on his part said the distribution of the seeds came at the right time when farmers do not have money to buy seeds due to the coronavirus pandemic, saying that it would boost their farming activities.

According to the representative of District Head of Tofa, *Makaman Bichi*, Alhaji Sunusi Abubakar, who spoke on behalf of the communities, said the assistance rendered to them by the CDA could not have come at a better time than now, noting that they would strictly follow the guidelines of growing the improved seeds.

The distribution of the seeds came at the right time when farmers do not have money to buy seeds due to the coronavirus pandemic

BUK Management Extends Tenure of Prof Jibrin as Director CDA

The University Principal Officers' at their 4th (2020) meeting held on Wednesday, 20th May, 2020 upon submission of end of tenure report approved that the tenure of Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin has been extended as Director of Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) up to the end of the ACE Impact Project.

According to a statement signed by the Registrar, Fatima Binta Mohammed, the Principal Officers considered Prof Jibrin's extension in order to ensure continuity and to make sure that the University does not lose the ACE Impact Grant with him being a signatory.

Recall that the CDA, Bayero University, Kano, won a World Bank Africa Centres of Excellence (ACE) Project Impact Grant along with 43 other centres from 12 West and Central African countries. The Centres were competitively selected under a \$300 million World Bank and French Development Agency- funded project aimed at scaling up postgraduate education and applied research.

Two ACEs in BUK Get Close to \$20m Grant for Research Development

Two research centres in Bayero University, Kano have secured close to \$20m grant from the World Bank for research development from 2014 to date the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, has said.

Speaking during the signing of Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between Bayero University's Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and Dantata Foods and Allied Products on Friday, 26th June, 2020, the Vice Chancellor said the CDA had in 2014 got the World Bank's \$8m to be a Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture. He added that last year, the CDA won another competitive grant for the Africa Centre of Excellence (ACE) Project for Impact, which will attract \$5m grant from the World Bank.

Professor Bello explained that the University was lucky to have another Africa Centre of Excellence for Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP), which secured a \$6m World Bank grant, saying that the two centres got close to \$20m grant for teaching, research and development activities.

Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin

The Minister of Education, Malam Adamu Adamu, formally launched the CDA's Africa Centres of Excellence Impact Project on Friday, 20th December, 2019 in which he congratulated the Bayero University and specifically the CDA for winning the World Bank's \$5m ACE Impact grant.

The CDA had achieved a lot in recent times including Bayero University's selection to host Partnership for Skills in Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology (PASET's) Pan African Regional Scholarship and Innovation Fund (RSIF) for its PhD programme.

The PhD Programme in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change was selected by the Executive Board of PASET as one of seven Universities to host PhD programmes and RSIF research and innovation activities.

Also, the French High Council for Evaluation of Research and Higher Education (HCERES) granted a five-year unreserved international accreditation status on two programmes of the CDA. The two programmes are: MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change and MSc Agronomy (Crops and Cropping Systems in Drylands).

Bayero University established the CDA in 2012 to provide quality training and applied research in response to the needs of the West and Central Africa (WCA) dryland region. Being a multidisciplinary Training and Research Centre, the CDA draws its core expertise from the faculties of Agriculture, Earth and Environmental Sciences, Social and Management Sciences, and Engineering to achieve its mandate as a regional Centre for Dryland Agriculture.

In 2014, the Centre won a competitive grant of \$8m from the World Bank to upgrade to a Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture.

Members of BUK Community Hail CDA over Supply of Fresh Farm Produce During Lockdown

Members of Bayero University Community heaved a sigh of relief during the lockdown restrictions due to the spread of coronavirus as the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) Farm provided fresh farm and poultry products at affordable rates.

The farm produce includes tomatoes, green pepper, red pepper, lettuce, cucumber, onions, eggs, broiler chicken and cockerels. All these are produced in the CDA Training and Research Farm.

On Thursday, 23rd April, 2020, when the lockdown in Kano was relaxed, hundreds of people trooped to the CDA Farm as early as 8am to get their produce having made bookings earlier through a Google form created by the Centre. Other people who did not make earlier bookings were given the opportunity to purchase the produce on the spot.

Many members of the University Community expressed appreciation with the CDA's gigantic strides of providing quality farm produce during this period and commended the centre for rising to the challenges of food security.

Professor Yusuf Adamu said CDA model is the way to go for BUK, saying that "we have the potentials and the knowledge. What we need is a little push for excellence."

Malama Asma'u Mahmood recounted that "I ordered for vegetables and I was surprised at the quantity. It was very fresh and at reasonable price."

According to Naziru Malami of the Faculty of Computer Science and Information Technology, "we give glory to

Almighty Allah for the CDA Farm. It brings relief to many BUK staff. The fresh tomatoes, green pepper and lettuce I bought from the farm last week are still being used in my house."

"It was a wonderful start. We hope to see great improvement in subsequent dealings. At least, we have something of this nature to call ours," Malam Mu'azu said.

The Deputy Dean, Faculty of Communication, Dr. Mainasara Kurfi, said, "This is a very good development. I was really impressed."

Recall that the CDA Research and Training Farm was commissioned by the Minister of Agriculture, Alhaji Muhammad Sabo Nanono on 20th December 2019.

"Our plan is to ensure that the Farm provides enough produce that will meet the demands of members of the university community and the neighbouring communities of Bayero University, Kano," said Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin at the commissioning ceremony.

The Chairperson of CDA Farm Marketing Committee and the Deputy Director, (Outreach and Publications), Professor Amina Mustapha had earlier assured the teeming staff members that the CDA planned to be providing fresh and quality produce for the consumption of members of Bayero University community. "The CDA has plans to have an outlet where staff members can purchase quality produce," she added.

According to her, if the lockdown persists, "the CDA would commence delivery to the Old Campus based on the placement of order by the prospective customers.

BUK, Malaysian Firm Donate Boreholes to 5 CDA Adopted Communities

Five adopted communities of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) were provided with boreholes and other accessories worth millions of naira by a Malaysian Firm, Diversatech Fertilizer in conjunction with Bayero University as part of efforts to ameliorate the acute water shortages faced by the communities.

Commissioning the water projects at Zangon Dan Audu, Wangara and Lengel villages on Saturday, 21st March, 2020, the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, said the project was a donation from a friend of the University in a far away Malaysia aimed at bringing succour to the host communities.

Professor Bello said when the management was contacted by the donor, it met to discuss on where to site the project and they come to the apt conclusion that the identified villages where in dare need of water.

“Although, the University was facing water scarcity, however, we felt that our neighbours are more in need than us, hence, our decision to carefully select these communities, because, while, we at the University had an alternative source, the villages on the other hand had none,” he declared.

According to him, the University is always considerate and mindful of the suffering of the neighbouring communities, assuring that it will be extending a helping hand whenever they have the financial strength. The University also gave a token

amount for the purchase of fuel and servicing of the generator to each of the communities.

Professor Bello commended the peaceful and harmonious relationship existing between the University and its host communities and urged them to continue with this for the mutual benefits and development of the University.

In their separates remarks, the Village Heads of Zangon Dan Audu, Alhaji Magaji Mai Unguwa; Wangara Alhaji Musa Yahaya and Lengel, Alhaji Mahmoud Idris respectively expressed delight at the gesture and promised to make judicious utilization of the project, pointing out that the project will go a long way in alleviating their water shortages.

They equally offered a special prayer for the growth and development of Bayero University, Kano and Diversatech Fertilizer, Malaysia, praying for Allah's peace, harmony and prosperity.

It could be recalled that earlier in January 2020 two other communities of Dididi/Lengel and Doka villages were provided with similar project.

The project consists of an overhead tank of 5,000 litre capacity water reservoir, a generator and water taps and a borehole with all its accessories.

The Vice Chancellor was accompanied by the Deputy Vice Chancellor (Academics) Professor Adamu Idris Tanko, Director Centre for Dryland Agriculture, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin and Dr.

CDA's FRESH FROM THE FARM

**CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE
BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO**

FOR BOOKING AND ENQUIRY

CALL: 07037716114, 08062670267

Email: cdabukfarms@gmail.com

Website: www.cda-buk.edu.ng